

Three particular polygonal and their origins.

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Abstract.

The three particular polygonal are:

- The logarithmic polygonal spiral with constant angular step.
- Regular polygons.
- The last divergent polygonal spiral, present in the resulting traces from formulation $\zeta(s) = \sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{1}{n^s}$ for $a=1/2$ and $b \neq 0$, where (a) is the real part of (s) and (b) is the coefficient of the imaginary part.

In this article I present for the first and third polygonal, two methods (one per polygonal) that allow you to identify the origin of the spirals.

For regular polygons both methods work.

1. Introduction.

Note:

- Below I will call the logarithmic polygonal spiral, with constant angular step "logarithmic polygonal".
- Below I will call the third polygonal "last divergent spiral".

I am conducting a research on the traces resulting from three formulations, of the Riemann zeta function.

In addition to being convinced that the Riemann Hypothesis is true, I am also convinced that the final divergence, always present, in the resulting traces from formulation $\zeta(s) = \sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{1}{n^s}$ for $a=1/2$ and $b \neq 0$, should not be considered an obstacle.

Analyzing, the traces in question, it is clear that the divergence final is due to the presence, of a last divergent spiral.

I discovered that given the same (s), the origin of this last divergent spiral, always coincides with the convergence points of the Riemann zeta function. To have at least one spiral in the trace, it must be $b \neq 0$.

With the conviction of the equivalence, between the origins of the last divergent spirals and the points of convergence, I decided to find a link, between the vectors of the last divergent spiral and its origin. Obviously it is same link must be valid for any value of (b), which determines the formation of at least one spiral.

Note: For the graphic analysis of the polygonal I use a two-dimensional CAD, therefore I transfer to the Cartesian plane, the traces resulting from the Riemann zeta function and treat them like normal ones polygonal.

2. The logarithmic polygonal.

The definition “constant angular step” comes from my method, designed to create and study polygonal spirals. The method in question provides the possibility, of using both the variable angular step and the constant angular step. To create the first polygonal spirals, I used an approach not based on the angular step. The consequence was that, the first polygonal spirals had a variable angular step. I had to use the constant angular step, to be able to create the logarithmic polygonal.

Now it is useful, the graphic method that I had designed to create logarithmic polygonal.

Given the formula in polar coordinates of the logarithmic spiral $r = a \cdot e^{b \cdot \theta}$, if I want, I can use it to build the base from which I then obtain the logarithmic polygonal.

I constructed Fig. 1 in the following way.

Having fixed the point (OR), I traced the horizontal straight line (r_1) passing through (OR), I then traced the straight line (r_2) passing through (OR) and forming with (r_1) the angle (Theta).

Point (A) is the starting point of what will become the logarithmic polygonal, the distance of (A) from (OR) corresponds to (a), in the formula in polar coordinates.

Wanting to use the logarithmic spiral formula, for locate point (B) I decide a value for (b) and then calculate (r). In in this case (L) and (Alpha) result accordingly.

Alternatively, I can decide the value of (r) or (Alpha), or the length (L) of the first segment.

Given (OR), (a) and (Theta) and then fixed one of the parameters (r), (b), (L) or (Alpha), I get the (B) point. The final result, will always be one logarithmic polygonal, provided that you continue, taking the following directions into account.

Once the points (OR) and (A) are fixed, the logarithmic polygonal can be divergent, as would result by completing and developing Fig. 1, or convergent, as would result by developing Fig. 2.

Fig. 2 represents what I call the “Basic Scheme”. In this case, I defined the point (B) by fixing the angle (Alpha). The next segments I drew them all parallel to the segment (A, B), their length results from their position and the angle (Theta) between (r_1) and (r_2).

The starting points of the segments parallel to the segment (A, B), are all on the straight line (r_1) and are defined by a circular arc with center at (OR) and passing through the point on the straight line (r_2), corresponding to the arrival point on the same straight line, as the previous segment.

To obtain the logarithmic polygonal from the "Basic Scheme", it is enough rotate the segments following the segment (A, B), one by one with the center in (OR). The rotation must bring the starting point of the segment, to correspond with the end point of the previous segment.

2.1 How I defined the first method.

The Basic Scheme shows very well what type of link exists, between segments that make up the logarithmic polygonal and its origin.

The method uses two pairs of segments of the logarithmic polygonal, which thanks to the characteristic of the logarithmic polygonal, being always equal to itself, can be at any distance from (OR).

To describe the method I use a single pair of segments.

Fig. 3 presents a Basic Scheme composed of only two segments, the rotated copy of segment (C, D) added to segment (A, B), forms the pair of segments (A, B) and (B, E), this is the pair I need.

Fig. 3 highlights that the angular step (Theta) is constant, highlights furthermore that the segment (B, E) can only form with the segment (A, B) the same angle (Theta).

In Fig. 4 I doubled the length of the segment (A, B) obtaining the segment (A, B1).

The idea of doubling the length of the segment (A, B) and performing a mirror copy of the segment (B, E), using the axis of symmetry of segment (A, B1), derives from the information entered in Fig. 3. The same information tells us that, the point (E1) belongs to the straight line (r1), which connects the point (A) with the origin (OR).

By repeating the operation with any other pair of segments, of the logarithmic polygonal, I define a second straight line, which can only intersect the first at the point (OR).

Fig. 5 shows a method equivalent to that illustrated in Fig. 4, that is what I chose as my first method.

In Fig. 5 I copied the segment (B, E), in parallel, making it coincide point (B) with point (A), I then made a mirror copy of the segment (A, E1), using the axis of symmetry of the segment (A, B).

The point (E2) belongs to the straight line (r1), which connects the point (A) with the origin (OR).

2.2 How I defined the second method.

If $b=0$ results in $r=a$, consequently the logarithmic spiral traces a circle, with center at its origin.

Obviously the same rule applies for the logarithmic polygonal and in the Basic Scheme only the segment (A, B) is apparently present, the other segments coincide with (A, B).

If (Θ) divides 2π into a number of equal parts, the polygonal draws a regular polygon.

To describe how I defined the second method, I use Fig. 6 e Fig. 7.

Fig. 6 shows the Basic Scheme that is obtained when $r=a$.

Fig. 7 highlights that in this case, it is sufficient to copy the segment (B, C) in parallel, making the copy of the point (B) coincide with the point (A).

The point (C1) belongs to the straight line (r2) which connects the point (B) with the origin (OR). To complete the second method, the procedure must be, repeated with a second pair of segments.

The two methods compared show that, they both work for the same polygonal only if $r=a$.

3. A fourth polygonal.

This polygonal spiral has constant inclination and length of the segments, the angular step is variable.

With the logarithmic polygonal it shares only the possibility of having $r=a$. Except for cases where $r=a$, neither method is applicable to this polygonal. Additional steps are required.

With the last divergent spiral, it shares the variable angular step and the tendency of the last divergent spiral, as the value of (n) , to have the characteristics of this fourth polygonal.

Fig. 8 presents two Basic Schemes, the one on the left is related to the fourth polygonal, the one on the right is related to the last divergent spiral, that I remember results from the function $\zeta(s) = \sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{1}{n^s}$, where $s=1/2+4*I$ and I used the first 30 segments.

To build the second Basic Scheme, I evidently followed the reverse operation, to that needed to obtain a polygonal spiral, starting from the Basic Scheme.

Fig. 8

In the one on the right, you can see that the segments tend to become parallel and to have the same length, but it remains a trend. Not near the origins, but both the resulting spirals, can be confused with the logarithmic polygonal.

4. The two methods applied to the three polygonal.

Fig. 9 schematizes the first method, applied to the traverse logarithmic. Fig. 10 schematizes both methods, applied to a regular polygon. Fig. 11 schematizes the second method, applied to the last divergent spiral.

For the last divergent spiral, the two pairs of segments must be consecutive. I decided to adopt this rule, also for the other two cases.

With reference to Fig. 9 and Fig. 11, point (A) is the starting point of the first segment used and the point (E) is the final point of the fourth segment.

Both methods can be used in either direction.

5. The second method applied to the last divergent spiral.

In this case, the second method does not provide the exact location of the origin, but an excellent approximation. The precision depends on the distance from (OR), understood as an increase in (n), of the four segments used. To achieve the precision offered by the zeta(s) function of PARI-GP, it would require much longer calculation times, at least for small values of (b). With my P.C. the zeta(s) function, allows to calculate the convergence point, only if the value of (b) is less than 7.000.000. With the second method, it is possible even with my P.C., to calculate the origin of the last divergent spiral, for values of (b) much greater than 7.000.000.

I think it is time to show what types of spiral I am talking of. I believe that the one hundred segments used, are sufficient, to provide a valid indication of the spirals in question.

On the left I have grouped the first hundred segments of eleven spirals, for which $a=1/2$ and $b=0.01 \div 1$. The origins, are indicated by, small circles.

In the center, enlarged ten times, the first hundred segments of the last divergent spiral, resulting from $a=1/2$ and $b=14.1347...$

On the right, enlarged two hundred times, one hundred segments of the last divergent spiral, resulting from $a=1/2$ and $b=1001.3494...$ As (f1) and (f2) indicate, in this case we are not talking about the first hundred segments, they start from $b/\pi+1000$.

I also tried the first method but it does not offer satisfactory results. The second method proves to adapt to all situations.

What convinced me of the validity of the second method applied to these spirals, were the results obtained with the spirals grouped on the left. For example, the spiral resulting from $b=0.01$ has an almost straight path, yet the second method locates the origin with increasing precision, increasing the distance from it of the four segments used.

I carried out the definition of the two methods and the first checks with CAD. I was able to carry out the most in-depth checks, thanks to PARI-GP. To use PARI-GP, I created a custom function. With this function, it is possible to obtain the coordinates of the initial and final points of any vector, which is found in the position defined by (n).

Having the coordinates of the five necessary points available, the subsequent instructions calculate the coordinate of (OR) and perform the comparison with the result provided by the zeta(s) function.

Below I have inserted the command lines for PARI-GP.

The data to provide are only (b) and (f). The value of (f) indicates the end of the summation, but also the value of (n) which determines the coordinates of the starting point of the first of the four vectors.

For $b \geq 2\pi$, the value of (n) from which the last divergent spiral begins, results from b/π . The precision of the result will therefore be greater, the more $f > b/\pi$.

Here are the command lines for PARI-GP.

```
Z(f,s)=sum(n=1,f,1/n^s)
a=1/2
b=
s=a+b*I
f=
fb1=f-2; fb2=f-1; Base=Z(fb1,s); Z(f,s)=Base+sum(n=fb2,f,1/n^s)
ZA=Z(f,s); xA=real(ZA); yA=imag(ZA); f=f+1; ZB=Z(f,s); xB=real(ZB); yB=imag(ZB)
f=f+1; ZC=Z(f,s); xC=real(ZC); yC=imag(ZC); f=f+1; ZD=Z(f,s); xD=real(ZD); yD=imag(ZD)
f=f+1; ZE=Z(f,s); xE=real(ZE); yE=imag(ZE)
xF=xC-xB+xA; yF=yC-yB+yA; xG=xE-xD+xC; yG=yE-yD+yC
\\----r1----
x1=xB; y1=yB; x2=xF; y2=yF; m1=(y1-y2)/(x1-x2); n1=y1-m1*x1
\\----r2----
x1=xD; y1=yD; x2=xG; y2=yG; m2=(y1-y2)/(x1-x2); n2=y1-m2*x1
\\-----
x=(n2-n1)/(m1-m2); y=m1*x+n1; OR=x+y*I
\\-----
Z=zeta(s)
DIST=sqrt((real(OR)-real(Z))^2+(imag(OR)-imag(Z))^2)
```

The last two command lines serve to compare the result of (OR), with the result of the zeta(s) function of PARI-GP. If you use values greater than 7.000.000 for (b), with a P.C. like mine, you cannot use the last two command lines. In any case don't need the comparison, if (b) is one of those values known as zero, of the Riemann zeta function.

These are, some of the results, I obtained with the tests.

f=10000000 (seven zero)	f=1000000000 (nine zero) (\p 50)
b=0.01 --> DIST=1.57... E-11	b=0.01 --> DIST=1.58... E-14
b=0.1 --> DIST=1.56... E-11	b=0.1 --> DIST=1.55... E-14
b=0.2 --> DIST=1.48... E-11	b=0.2 --> DIST=1.48... E-14
b=0.3 --> DIST=1.38... E-11	b=0.3 --> DIST=1.38... E-14
b=0.4 --> DIST=1.28... E-11	b=0.4 --> DIST=1.28... E-14
b=0.5 --> DIST=1.18... E-11	b=0.5 --> DIST=1.18... E-14
b=0.6 --> DIST=1.09... E-11	b=0.6 --> DIST=1.09... E-14
b=0.7 --> DIST=1.01... E-11	b=0.7 --> DIST=1.01... E-14
b=0.8 --> DIST=9.50... E-12	b=0.8 --> DIST=9.50... E-15
b=0.9 --> DIST=8.96... E-12	b=0.9 --> DIST=8.95... E-15
b=1.0 --> DIST=8.50... E-12	b=1.0 --> DIST=8.50... E-15

(OR) values obtained with (b) values, known as zero of the Riemann zeta function.

f=100000000 (eight zero)

b=14.13472514173469379045725198

OR= -1.51... E-13 - 0.73... E-13*I

f=2000000000 (nine zero) (\p 100)

b=14.13472514173469379045725198

OR= 9.29... E-16 - 1.63... E-15*I

f=4000000000 (nine zero) (\p 50)

b=10000.06534541453531475023...

OR= -2.51... E-16 + 6.09... E-16*I

f=1000000000 (nine zero) (\p 100)

b=2000000000.333438278595189...

OR= -6.44... E-15 - 1.62... E-14*I

f=4000000000 (nine zero)

b=2000000000.333438278595189...

OR= -6.40... E-16 + 4.20... E-16*I

f=1000000000 (nine zero) (\p 100)

b=14.13472514173469379045725198

OR= -4.12... E-15 + 3.33... E-15*I

f=4000000000 (nine zero) (\p 50)

b=14.13472514173469379045725198

OR= -9.65... E-17 + 6.55... E-16*I

f=4000000000 (nine zero) (\p 50)

b=1500000.612817757350274114...

OR= 3.85... E-16 + 5.35... E-16*I

f=2000000000 (nine zero)

b=2000000000.333438278595189...

OR= -2.98... E-15 + 2.22... E-15*I

On zenodo.org, a preprint of mine is available at the following address

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dedicated to the traces resulting from Riemann zeta function.

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